

Eosinophilia in Barabanki Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Background: Eosinophilia is frequently reported in routine investigations in the Barabanki region of Uttar Pradesh. The objective is to study the clinical profile and prevalence of parasitosis in adolescents presenting with eosinophilia and to find any gender-specific association in eosinophilia severity.

Methods: This prospective hospital-based observational study was carried out in the Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Barabanki for over 1 year on a purposive sample of 325 adolescents aged 10-19 years presenting with eosinophilia. History, examination, eosinophil count and stool microscopy was done.

Results: Of the total 325 adolescents, 60% were boys, 66.8% were from rural areas, 60% were from lower socioeconomic status, 27.1% had unhygienic means of stool disposal and 58.8% used underground water for drinking purposes. Almost one-third were asymptomatic. Common presenting symptoms were abdominal pain in 93 (28.6%), allergic symptoms in 46 (14.2%), cough in 42 (12.9%), respiratory distress in 18 (5.5%), diarrhoea in 14 (4.3%), constipation in 13 (4%). Worm infestation was reported in stool sample of 21.2%. The total mean (SD) absolute eosinophil count (AEC) was 3.89 (4.83). The total mean (SD) AEC for boys was 3.79 (4.64) and for girls was 4.04 (5.11). No gender-specific difference was found in eosinophilia severity.

Conclusions: The main causes of eosinophilia in the Barabanki region seems to be parasitic infestation. Simple measures, such as having toilets in every home, proper hand washing and clean water supply, can be helpful.

Keywords: *Eosinophil, Parasitosis, open defecation*

INTRODUCTION :

Eosinophilia is characterized by an increase in the number of eosinophils in the tissues and/or blood. Blood eosinophil counts are more easily and frequently measured than tissue eosinophil counts, which require inspection of biopsied samples (1). In the bone marrow, normal eosinophil percentages range from 1% to 6%, whereas in the peripheral blood, normal eosinophil percentages range from 3% to 5%, equal to an absolute peripheral eosinophil count (AEC) of 0.35 to $0.5 \times 10^9/L$ (2). A blood eosinophil level higher than $0.5 \times 10^9/L$ is considered eosinophilia. Mild eosinophilia is defined as $0.5-1.5 \times 10^9/L$, moderate eosinophilia as $>1.5-5.0 \times 10^9/L$, and severe eosinophilia as $>5.0 \times 10^9/L$ (3).

Eosinophilia in the blood is either a cytokine-mediated reactive event (secondary) or a manifestation of an underlying hematological malignancy (primary). In under-developed and developing countries, secondary eosinophilia is frequently connected with parasitosis, while in the West, it is usually associated with allergic disorders (4). The commonest cause of eosinophilia in countries like India is high parasitic infestation due to the inadequate sanitation facilities and associated unhygienic living conditions (5). The present study was conducted with the primary objective to study the clinical profile and prevalence of parasitosis in adolescents presenting with eosinophilia. Secondary objective was to investigate any gender-specific association in eosinophilia severity.

METHODS :

This prospective hospital-based observational study was carried out in the department of pediatrics, and department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, over a period of 1 year, from November 2020 to October 2021. A purposive sample of adolescents aged 10-19 years attending the outpatient department or admitted to the inpatient department, who had blood eosinophil count $> 0.5 \times 10^9/L$ were taken into the study after obtaining the informed consent from parents and assent from the adolescents. Adolescents who were not the residents of Barabanki district were excluded.

A detailed history was taken with a systematically pre-designed pro forma. A complete physical examination was done to rule out any systemic disorder. Blood samples were drawn after a minimum of 8 hours of fasting from all the children and sent for reporting of absolute eosinophil counts. Stool samples were sent for microbiological analysis to detect any parasitosis.

The data collected were analyzed statistically with the help of SPSS software (version 25.0). Continuous variables were expressed as mean±SD. The comparison of the data was performed using t-test. p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS :

We recruited a total of 325 subjects, including 195 boys (60%). Among the total adolescents, 154 (47.4%), 116 (35.7%), and 55 (16.9%) were in the early adolescence (10-13 years), mid-adolescence (14-16 years), and late adolescence (17-19 years) age groups respectively. In our study, 217 adolescents (66.8%) were from rural areas. Most of the adolescents were from lower socio-economic status (195, 60%). Toilets were used for defecation by 237 (72.9%) adolescents while 88 (27.1%) defecated in open. The drinking water supply source was underground water in 191 (58.8%) and river water in 134 (41.2%). The demographic characteristics of the adolescents are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic details of the study population [n=325]

Parameters		Boys	Girls	Total
Age Group	Early Adolescence (10-13 years)	86	68	154
	Mid Adolescence (14-16 years)	75	41	116
	Late Adolescence (17-19 years)	34	21	55
Location	Rural	126	91	217
	Urban	69	39	108
Socioeconomic status	Upper	18	14	32
	Middle	67	31	98
	Lower	110	85	195
Stool disposal	Use of toilet for defecation	141	96	237
	Open defecation	54	34	88
Drinking water supply	Underground water supply	110	81	191
	River water supply	85	49	134

In the clinical profile, 99 (30.5%) were asymptomatic and were detected during a routine blood examination. Common presenting symptoms in adolescents with eosinophilia were abdominal pain in 93 (28.6%), cough in 42 (12.9%), allergic symptoms in 46 (14.2%), respiratory distress in 18 (5.5%), diarrhoea in 14 (4.3%), and constipation in 13 (4%) [Figure 1]. We documented worm infestation in stools samples of 69 (21.2%) of adolescents with eosinophilia.

Figure 1: Common presenting symptoms in Adolescents with eosinophilia [n=325]

In present study, 159 (48.9%) adolescents had mild, 118 (36.3%) had moderate and 48 (14.8%) had severe eosinophilia [Figure 2].

Figure 2: Distribution of subjects according to the severity of eosinophilia* [n=325]

The maximum differential percentage of eosinophil count found was 72%. The total mean (\pm SD) absolute eosinophil count was $3.89 (\pm 4.83) \times 10^9/L$. The maximum absolute eosinophil count (AEC) was $23.40 \times 10^9/L$ and the minimum AEC was $0.66 \times 10^9/L$. Table 2 depicts the mean and standard deviation of absolute eosinophil counts among boys and girls according to severity. There was no statistically significant difference found between the two genders in total cases or any level of severity of eosinophilia.

Table 2 : Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) of Absolute eosinophil count (AEC) according to severity [n=325]

Absolute eosinophil count (AEC) Severity	Boys (mean \pm SD)	Girls (mean \pm SD)	p	Total (mean \pm SD)
Mild ($0.5-1.5 \times 10^9/L$)	1.32 ± 0.38	1.25 ± 0.30	0.2200	1.21 ± 0.38
Moderate ($>1.5-5 \times 10^9/L$)	3.25 ± 1.31	3.71 ± 1.16	0.0522	3.44 ± 1.26
Severe ($>5 \times 10^9/L$)	13.29 ± 5.40	14.83 ± 5.42	0.3397	13.90 ± 5.40
Total (mean+SD)	3.79 ± 4.64	4.05 ± 5.11	0.6350	3.89 ± 4.83

DISCUSSION

Eosinophilia is a frequent finding, usually discovered by chance during a normal hematological examination. In the present study, 66.8% of adolescents were from rural areas, 60% were from low socioeconomic status, 27.1% had unhygienic means of stool disposal and 58.8% used underground water for drinking purposes. With governments initiatives, there has been a drastic decrease in open defecation and increase in the provision of toilets in each home, but still more health education needs to be imparted to bring a change in the mentality of the people who prefer to defecate in open even when they have a toilet facility.

In the present study, 99 (30.5%) adolescents with eosinophilia were asymptomatic which was similar to previous research done by Schulte C et al who showed about one-third of the patients with eosinophilia were asymptomatic (6). In our study, among 226 symptomatic adolescents with eosinophilia, the most common presenting symptom was abdominal pain in 93 (28.6%), followed by allergic symptoms in 46 (14.2%) and cough in 42 (12.9%).

Parasitic infestation and atopy are two important causes of eosinophilia but etiology remains idiopathic in most patients (6,7). In developed countries, allergy and atopy is the leading cause while in developing countries parasitic infestation is

the leading cause (8,9,10). Barabanki, in eastern Uttar Pradesh, has a largely rural population with insufficient access to safe drinking water or sanitary facilities. The practice of defecating in open is a typical cause of worm infection. This might explain the high rate of reported worm infection in our research population, which was 21.2% which is comparable to a study done by Makkar A et al, which reported parasitic infestation to be the more common etiology of eosinophilia than allergy (11).

In the present study, the mean (SD) of absolute eosinophil count (AEC) according to severity were 1.21 (0.38), 3.44 (1.26), and 13.90 (5.40) in mild, moderate, and severe categories of eosinophilia respectively. The mean (SD) was comparable in both boys and girls and no statistically significant gender-specific association was found. According to Butt NM et al, there is no sex or ethnic variation in the eosinophil count (12).

CONCLUSION

In Barabanki, eosinophilia is frequently reported in routine investigations as an incidental finding. From the present study, the main cause of eosinophilia in this region seems to be parasitic infestation. Simple health initiatives, such as having toilets in every home; proper hand washing before taking meals and after defecation; provision of clean water supply; and health education to all regarding maintenance of personal hygiene can be helpful in reducing the load of parasitosis and subsequently eosinophilia in the area.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical approval: Approval taken by the Institute Ethics Committee.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

There is no conflict of interest to be declared by the authors.

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